

Lukasiewicz 25.02.25

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Sample Name: Proszki

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Image

Live Map 1

ElementOverlay

- C K
- O K
- Si K

C K_ROI (76)

O K_ROI (49)

Si K_ROI (67)

kV: 5 Mag: 500 Takeoff: 35 Live Time(s): 1 Amp Time(μs): 50 Resolution:(eV) 138

Sum Spectrum

eZAF Quant Result - Analysis Uncertainty: 32.74 %

Element	Weight %	MDL	Atomic %	Net Int.	Error %
C K	26.9	0.05	45.5	1080.6	10.2
O K	3.2	0.02	4.1	525.5	7.4
Si K	69.8	0.02	50.4	8652.6	5.6